

A Model of Interaction of Rigid Fibers in an Orthotropic Composite Rope

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Abstract. The purpose of research is to construct an algorithm for calculating a stress-strain state of a multilayer orthotropic composite rope. Research methodology involves constructing and solving the interaction model of parallel reinforcing rigid fiber elements regularly placed in layers connected through an elastic material. A method for calculating a stress-strain state of a multilayer orthotropic composite rope is developed. The scientific novelty of research is in the establishment of a dependency for distribution of internal loading forces in reinforcing rigid fibers on stay rope parameters. The distribution of internal loading forces in reinforcing fibers depends on the amount and relative location of fibers in a stay rope. Along the length, the stress-strain state of a rope depends on a square root of the ratio of shear modulus of elastic matrix and tensile rigidity of fibers. The practical value of the research is in that the presented method allows determining the rope stress-strain state during the designing stage of a permanent structure. This is based on structural parameters and mechanical properties of components of a composite rope and conditions of its interaction with the structure, thereby increasing reliability and operation efficiency of the structure, in particular, the cable-stayed bridge.

Introduction

The ropes are used for suspension of spans in bridge structures with long spans. This solution is more technological and allows reducing the construction time [1]. In [2], a method of analytical calculation of a cable-stayed structure is suggested. The use of SCAD software is suggested for selection of rational parameters of elements of a cable-stayed bridge in [3].

The main elements of a cable-stayed bridge are span structures held by stay ropes. According to the standard [4], wires with a diameter of 3 to 30 mm must be used in stay ropes. Gaps between the wires must be filled. Stay ropes are affected by the environment, wires corrode, and wind loads affect them. It is possible to protect ropes from environmental influences by using ropes covered with elastic material (rubber, polyurethane). Such composite ropes can be multi-layered. It is possible to use several cables with sufficiently smaller diameters as reinforcing elements. Such cables of smaller diameter are made of wires of a smaller diameter. Ultimate strength is higher for wires of a smaller diameter. Reducing cable diameter in a stay rope reduces its mass. Accordingly, the use of wires with a much smaller diameter than that established by the standard [4] in stay ropes partially compensates the increase of stay rope mass caused by filling the gaps between cables with elastic material. By selecting the amount of cable layers, it is possible to give the rope a shape that reduces rope resistance to wind loads.